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**ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SWEET POTATO,
COWPEA AND MAIZE COVERS IN SEDIMENT YIELD AND SURFACE
RUN-OFF IN SOIL EROSION MANAGEMENT IN PLATEAU STATE,
NIGERIA**

NGUPAS K. DAYIL¹, MAHMUD ABABUKAR², ISHAYA K. SAM UILA³.

¹*Department of Geography and Planning, Faculty of Environmental Sciences University of Jos, Nigeria.*

^{2 & 3}*Department of Geography, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Nasarawa State University Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.*

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-6947-2216>

¹ *Corresponding Author*

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ABSTRACT

Most soil over the years, are unable to achieve their peak performance of providing effective production (yield) due to lack of focus or poor knowledge of soil erosion undermining the quantity and quality of agricultural productivity and performance in Plateau State Nigeria. The study seeks to assess the level of the effectiveness of sweet potato, cowpea and maize covers in checking soil erosion of sediment yield and surface run-off of the study area. The study was an experimental field designed in the three (3) senatorial zone of Plateau State; with one local government of each zone used for field data collection for the analysis. This study covered a period of one-year (2020). Observations were proper recorded and analyzed using the unit of measurements: for sediment yield kilograms (kg) and for surface run-off was volume (cm³) using bottle-funnel as instrument for data collection. The results of the analysis shows that all the three (3) senatorial zones of the study fields with covers have less sedimentary yield and surface run-off of (126A,124B,104C and 198.1A, 176.6B and 576.9C respectively, compared to the bare-land with the highest total analysis of 1.288.6sy and 210sr in all the three (3) zones of Plateau State. This indicate that crop canopy covers can positively managed sediment yield collection on the field, while on the other hand, surface run-off under crop canopy covers has less total analysis in all the three (3) zone of study area; as

compared to the bare-land with the highest total analysis of the table. The result indicates that crop canopy covers are effective and efficient in protecting both sediment yield and surface run-off of the field. To mitigate the negative impact of soil erosion by the farmers, it is recommended that farmers, stakeholders and government embarked on the production of cover crops to minimize the action of rainfall on the field and increases food security of the state.

KEYWORDS: Sediment yield collection, surface run-off collection, farmers, crop canopy cover, flat beds, field, bare-land.

INTRODUCTION

Soil is the loose surface material that covers most land. It consists of inorganic particles and organic matter. Soil provides the structural support for agricultural plants and also their source of water and nutrients. Soils vary greatly in their chemical and physical properties. Soil provides a host of perfect services for both people and planet. Soil puts food on our plates, purifies our water, protects us against flooding and combats drought. It is also key to tackling climate change as it captures and stores vast amounts of carbon. Thus, there is no food security without healthy soils. Soil is our life support system, soil anchors roots, holds water and stores nutrients. Soils are home to earthworms, termites and a myriad of micro-organism (Wuepper, 2020).

Srivastava (2007) and Liu (2023), defined soil as naturally occurring unconsolidated weathered material on the surface of the earth that has been influenced by parent material, climate (including effects of moisture and temperature), macro and micro -organism and relief all acting over a period of time to produce soil that may have different physical, chemical, microbiological, biological and morphological properties from the material from which it was derived and serve as natural medium for growth of land plants. Soil erosion implies the lowering, washing, and wearing (eating away) of the top soil surface which serves as a natural habitat (medium) for plants and animals' growth and development (agriculture) through a geomorphological process caused by water and wind such as corrosion, abrasion, denudation etc. (Suresh, 2009). However, Tilman et al (2011) observed that the history of soil erosion is an integral part of agriculture.

All over the world, wherever human being started agricultural operations, there exists the problem of soil erosion in some extent that is why soil technologist and soil scientist are of the opinions that soil takes many years to be created, but it can be destroyed in few seconds by natural and artificial forces. Soil erosion decreases soil fertility, which can negatively affect crop yields. It also sends soil-laden water downstream, which can create heavy layers of sediment that prevent streams and rivers from flowing smoothly and can eventually lead to flooding. Once soil erosion occurs, it is more likely to happen again. Soil erosion reduces cropland productivity and contributes to the pollution of adjacent watercourses, wetlands and lakes. Soil erosion can be a slow process that continues relatively unnoticed or can occur at an alarming rate, causing serious loss of topsoil (organic soil) (Wikimedia, 2024).

Salhi (2023) observed that world-records reveal that half of the topsoil on the planet has been lost in the last 150 years due to soil erosion. In addition to erosion, soil quality is affected by other aspects of agriculture. These impacts include compaction, loss of soil structure, nutrient degradation, and soil salinity. The world countries experiencing soil erosion are classified into two groups, the group of most erosion and group of less erosion. The group of most erosion includes, Caribbean countries, Brazil, Central African countries, and parts of Southeast Asia which experiencing most severe erosion of more than 70% of their arable land. In contrast, Australia,

Canada, Saharan countries, Russia and most of the European Union are only losing 3% of their arable land to severe erosion (Wuepper, 2020).

In Africa, land degradation and soil erosion are becoming increasingly problematic due rapidly developing urban areas, particularly in major port cities. Uncontrolled expansion and human pressures are hindering planning, adaptation, and conservation efforts. Some African countries liable to soil erosion are the coastal nations of West and Central Africa which include, Senegal, Gambia, Sierra-Leone, Cameroon, Gabon, Angola, Ghana, Togo, Benin and Nigeria which have low lying lagoonal coasts that are susceptible to erosion and hence are threatened by sea-level rise, particularly because most of the countries in this area have major erosion issues rapidly expanding (Salhi, 2023).

In Nigeria, soil erosion is a severe soil degradation problem that endangers the actualization of Sustainable development Goals. It affects agricultural production by reducing soil fertility via topsoil translocation, leading to soil quality deterioration. Soil erosion occurs primarily when dirt is left exposed to strong winds, hard rains, and flowing water. In some cases, human activities, especially farming and land clearing, leave soil vulnerable to erosion (Wikimedia, 2024). Erosion in Nigeria is more pronounced in the Southern, Eastern and Northern parts of the country. Soil erosion is thus, the detachment and movement of soil material by the natural or accelerated and also by human activity. Depending on the local landscape and weather conditions, erosion may be very slow or very rapid. Natural erosion has sculptured landforms on the uplands and built landforms on the lowlands (Liu, 2023) and Salhi, 2023)

In light of this, Wikimedia (2024) suggested that the best preventive measures of soil erosion was by replanting of cover crops, or mulching to reduce soil erosion in the initial stages because only vegetation covers protects or mitigates fields from destruction by water run-offs, raindrops, and wind. In severe cases, the impact can be mitigated with terrace farming to check dams. Judicious management of the soil resource is essential to the sustainability of agriculture to meet the basic food needs of an expanding world population. The world population was projected to rise from 5.3 billion people in 1990 to 8.5 billion in 2025 and 10 billion by 2050 (Bongaarts, 2002). Out of the projected yearly increase of 90 million, 86 million will occur in the developing countries of the tropics and subtropics as posited by Owoputi & Stolte, (2014) and (Abebe 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Study Area:

Plateau State is located in North-Central Nigeria between latitudes $8^{\circ} 22'$ and $10^{\circ} 24'$ North and longitudes $8^{\circ} 32'$ and $10^{\circ} 38'$ East with a total landmass of 26, 901 km². The state has three (3) senatorial zones namely Northern senatorial zone, Central senatorial zone and Southern zone. The state is divided into 17 Local Government Area (LGAs). The National Population Commission estimated the population of the state in 2019 to be 3.5 million persons.

Plateau State is considered as the home of agricultural in Nigeria as all the three (3) zones are highly embarking on quantity and quality production of different crop species. The economy of Plateau State consists of varied human activities, prominent among these are: farming, civil services, industrialization, mining, trading and animal rearing. The climate is the tropical type with peak annual rainfall between June and September and the average room temperature is about 28 degrees centigrade. The favorable climatic conditions associated with relief favour the production

of crops like Irish potatoes, apples, grapes, wheat barley and so many varieties of vegetables both for direct consumption and or use by the manufacturing firms. The other farm produce of the state include yam, maize, sweet potatoes, acha, tomatoes, sorghum, green beans which are grown throughout the year through rain-fed at wet season and irrigation using the ponds water and streams during the dry seasons.

Plateau State

Source: (GIS UNIJOS 2020)

Fig. 2 Map of Plateau State showing the study locations

Study Procedure

A bottle-funnel was developed to generate and collect data from the designed field in the three (3) senatorial zones of the study area. The funnel containing cotton wool fixed into the funnel for collecting the sediment yield of the field, while the bottle was used for collecting the surface run-off of the field respectively in the three (3) senatorial zones. The study was carried out during the rainy season to enable the researcher make a proper observation of the erosive forces of the rainfall in eroding the field under the crop covers. Immediately the rainfall stops the bottle-funnel, the sediment yield and surface run-off were taken into the laboratory for measurement and data collected for analysis. An Anova and Test of significance of variance were satisfactorily used for the analysis to obtain results that were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plateau State Level of Covers Effectiveness.

The essential efficiency of crop canopy covers and the effectiveness of the covers in soil erosion management in Plateau State is highly dependent on the covers production, utilization period of establishment on the field and widely distribution of the covers as well as farmers knowledge on covers as a mitigation measures of soil erosion management, in Plateau State, Nigeria. The effectiveness of covers in soil erosion management were assessed, sediment yield collection and surface run-off collection as shown in Table 1

Table 1 Sediment Yield and Surface run—off under different crop covers in the study area

Field	Zone	A		B		C		diff	diff sy	diff sr	diff sr
		Sy	Sr	Sy	Sr	Sy	Sr				
Sp (F1)	8	18.9	12	15.8	6	53.2	4	6	3.1	37.34	
CP (F2)	14	24.6	18	19.8	8	69.9	4	10	4.8	50.1	
MZ (F3)	28	28.2	26	32.8	24	92.2	2	2	4.6	59.4	
BL (F4)	74	76	126.4	68	1088.2	66	301.6	8	18.2	253.4	

Total	126	198.1	124	176.6	104	576.9	18	20	30.7	400.3
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Analysis

Source; Field work 2020

Key;

sy = sediment yield

sr = surface run-off

sp = sweet potato

cp = cowpea

mz = maize

bl = bare-land (control treatment)

ab =variation between A and B (sy)

bc = variation between B and C (sy)

unit measurement =kilogramme (kg) for sediment yield

ab =variation between A and B (sr)

bc = variation between B and C (sr)

unit of measurement =volume (cm³) for surface run-off

The results of the analysis from table 1 shows the determination of the level of sediment yield and surface run-off collection of the three fields. The results indicates that in zone A, field A had sediment yield total of 126 kg, field B had a total of 124 kg while field C had a total of 104 kg. The results reveal that field A had the highest sediment yield of zone A followed by field B and lastly field C. In the same zone A, the results further shows that field A had a surface run-off total of 198.1 cm³, field B had a total surface run-off of 176.6 cm³ and field C had 576.9 cm³ which revealed that field C had the highest surface run-off followed by field A and lastly field C.

On the same table, results of sediment yield and surface run-off in zone A reveal that; sp had 8 kg, cp had 14 kg, mz had 28 kg and bl had 74 kg total of sediment yield and the results reveal that the bl has the highest sediment yield, followed by mz, cp and lastly sp. The results indicate that all cover crops can significantly mitigate or control sediment yield of the field as compared to the bare-land (bl) with the highest sediment yield. On the same zone A, of the surface run—off sp had 18.9 cm³, cp had 24.6 cm³, mz had 28.2 cm³ and bl has a total of 76 cm³ volume surface run—off of the field. The results reveal that all cover crops are significantly supporting the effectiveness of soil erosion management in the study area. The results further showed the variations in terms of

the difference between the three fields where fields A and B had difference 18 kg, fields B and C had 20 kg in terms of sediment yield as well as the variation in terms of ab and bc of the field covers, the sp had 4 kg, cp had 4 kg, mz had 2 kg kg and bl had 301.6 kg for ab and sp had 6 kg, cp had 10 kg, mz had 2 kg, and bl had 8 kg respectively. The variation of ab and bc of sediment yield reveals that covers can positively and significantly effective in soil erosion management in Plateau State. From the findings of ab and bc of the table revealed that the variation has less sediment yield in all the cover crops indicating the effectiveness of covers as compared to the bare-land with the highest total differences

On the other hand, the table also revealed the difference of AB and BC of the total surface run-off of the three fields of the study area indicating that field ab had a total surface run—off of 30.7 cm³ and field **B and C** had 400.3 cm³ volume of surface run-off differences.

Result indicates that AB has lesser surface run-off compared to BC with the higher surface run-off of the three fields. But on the basis of covers, in terms of surface run—off differences, ab under sp had 3.1 cm³, cp had 4.8 cm³, mz had 4.6 cm³ and bl had 18.2 cm³, and differences bc has sp had 37.3 cm³ ,cp had 50.1 cm³ ,mz had 59.4 cm³ and bl has a total of 253.6 cm³ respectively. The results from differences pfab and bc indicate that all the covers are capable of mitigating soil erosion in the study area as compared to the bare—land with the highest total of surface run-off.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study on the assessment of the effectiveness of sweet potato, cowpea and maize covers in sediment yield and surface run-off in soil erosion management in Plateau State, Nigeria, concludes that the results of the three (3) fields that crop canopy covers prevents losses of sediment yield and surface run-off of the study area. The causes of soil erosion in the study areas are illegal deforestation, bush burning, and feeling of cover trees for fuel and energy and also agricultural practices.

The recommendations based on the findings of this study are:

- i. Any agricultural system or practices that have implication directly on the soil should be stopped by the farmers in the study area to keep the soil alive and functional in agricultural production.
- ii. Farmers in the study area should embark on crop canopy covers farming as it mitigates soil erosion and also provides food security for the population in and outside the study area.
- iii. Government should step up, re-enforcement and regulates the illegal deforestation, excessive mining activities, falling of cover trees for fuel and energy and also bush burning which tend to prevent regeneration of covers in the study area.

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